

KEY TRENDS IN SUPPLY PEACE AND RESTORATION

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Abstract. *"Holy Motherland, it is an honor to protect it!" ideas about the important principles of the idea and the factors of civic duty were put forward.*

Keywords: *to promote and inculcate the ideas of patriotism, responsibility, spirituality, enlightenment, peace and stability in the minds of young people.*

Social-political, spiritual-educational and trade-economic issues are gaining importance in the context of wide-scale reforms in the modernized Uzbekistan. That's why the President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoev, in the increasing position of Uzbekistan in the world community, relying on the principle of peace, stability and humanity, it is most important to put the lives, dreams, pains and dreams of every person living in our country in the center of our attention and to increase the effectiveness of the tasks in this regard. is putting it on the agenda as an issue. From the point of view of social policy, the issues of creating local jobs, opening wide opportunities for the development of entrepreneurship and private property, caring for youth, women, the elderly and disabled, and paying attention to needy people are reflected in the adopted state programs. Also, in accordance with our future plans, Uzbekistan is boldly advancing from national recovery to national growth.

Decision PQ-3898 of August 4, 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoev "On the fundamental improvement of the system of raising the moral and educational level of the military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and moral and educational work in the Armed Forces system introduced on this basis in accordance with the concept of increasing the effectiveness of "Holy Motherland, it is an honorable duty to protect it!" idea was put forward[1] Also, in the Armed Forces system, every Friday of the week is designated as the "Day of Moral Elevation and Patriotism", and it is necessary to encourage the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. The goal is to protect the sovereignty of our country, territorial integrity, and the peace of our people with loyalty, which is recognized as the highest task.

Wide-scale reforms are being implemented in our country to strengthen peace and stability, ensure human rights, freedoms and interests, comprehensively develop our country, and raise its prestige in the international arena.

Therefore, according to the seven priority directions defined in the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the state program "Year of attention to people and quality education", "Prosperous village", "Prosperous neighborhood", "Every family is an entrepreneur", "Youth is our future", Based on the meaning and content of reforms carried out within the framework of important programs and plans such as "Five positive initiatives", the main ideological principles of this decree put the human factor in a high position.

We are convinced that the policy of Uzbekistan, which is on the path of developing a legal democratic state and a fair civil society based on the free market economy under the leadership of our President, focuses on the development of the society. The activities of public organizations, political institutions and mass media are synchronized with today's processes in the implementation of comprehensive reforms aimed at the liberalization of state administration, improvement of the state and society. The fact that the state and its policies are focused only on the benefit of the people, on ensuring the peace and stable life of the country's citizens is reflected in the adopted laws, presidential decrees and decisions, and is implemented in life. Along with determining the material and cultural image of the society, this has a positive effect on the spiritual and educational, moral thinking and worldview of the citizens of the country. That is why it creates an opportunity to harmonize the relations between the state and the citizens, the authorities and the population based on justice. Under the leadership of our head of state, our people live peacefully, positive economic changes are taking place step by step in our country. New opportunities are being opened for entrepreneurial, knowledgeable, hardworking people.

The principle that the people should serve our people and not the state agencies is being widely applied in life. Life itself shows the necessity of achieving justice in the legal system, ensuring citizens' confidence in the future, and raising the human factor by making an impartial assessment of the activities of state bodies.

Ensuring the viability and enforcement of adopted laws should become a priority in society. Now, in the state and non-state sector, as well as in the entire production, there is a need for specialist employees, employees who quickly get involved in economic reforms, and personnel who meet the requirements of market relations and the requirements of modern world technology. Therefore, it is an important task to move from general production to production based on advanced technologies, to increase the volume of export of products, and to train employees who think in a new way in today's market conditions.

The fact that, on the initiative of the President, every Thursday of the week is declared as Crime Prevention Day in our country, as well as the fact that mobile court hearings are held, and the system of opening and effective communication with the people is being established, it is a proof of the practical manifestation of democratic principles. [2]

Deepening and expanding the scope of structural reforms, modernizing the economy, ensuring stable and balanced macroeconomic indicators, making investments, developing free economic zones, strengthening the private ownership sector and further improving the favorable environment for business, employment of the population as an important condition for the population's income and standard of living. The wide-scale reforms implemented by the head of our state in terms of ensuring employment and promoting exports in all respects are recognized as an important factor determining the development of our country. Now, the members of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis and the deputies of the Legislative Chamber meet with their constituents on the last ten days of every month and develop measures to legally solve the problems that are bothering the population, and the fact that the authorities are not indifferent to the appeals of the citizens creates a basis for people to live with a sense of involvement in the changes taking place in society.

At the moment, the consistent continuation of a well-thought-out tight monetary policy is seen as an important issue for job creation.

Today's world is experiencing an information onslaught. For this reason, information acquisition is becoming one of the most urgent issues in the population's thinking. Now, while analyzing the interest, mood, and social status of all individuals and social groups, providing jobs to the unemployed remains an important issue. Development of non-state sector is also one of the most important effective means. Because the non-state sector is considered as the starting link in

the formation of civil society. In these processes, man appears as a subject of society in solving his social problems. We must admit that due to our carelessness, indifference and some of our shortcomings in our work, some young people have fallen under the influence of criminal groups, extremists and alien, destructive ideas.

Great creative works are being carried out throughout our country. Shahapy - the appearance of our villages is becoming more beautiful day by day, affordable housing and infrastructure networks are being built for the population on the basis of exemplary projects. Renewable electricity, clean drinking water and natural gas supplies are improving. Don't you say that the abundance of goods in the shops in the bazaars, the abundance of our tables? All this, first of all, is due to our independence, and moreover, the peace and tranquility prevailing in our country. It motivates all of us to sacrifice.

Ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in our country was considered a priority of our state policy. Representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples living in our country have united in 138 national-cultural centers and live peacefully as children of a big family under the slogan "Uzbekistan is our common home". At the root of this is a great humanitarian policy. In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2017, the Committee on International Relations and Friendly Relations with Foreign Countries was established under the Cabinet of Ministers. The main goal of this is to consistently continue the state policy aimed at ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and tolerance in our society.

In today's world, where the process of globalization has intensified, global competition and mutual opposition are growing, threats such as radicalism, terrorism, extremism, proselytism, and "mass culture" are expanding, we must always be alert and vigilant. Life itself requires us to further increase our mobilization through the ideas of "Protect your own home", "Protect your own child". We need to educate our young men and women in the spirit of patriotism to ensure the integrity of the country's borders, to strengthen the combat potential of our Armed Forces. [3]. Also, the fact that our state is at the center of social and political affairs during today's pandemic, and the organization of generosity and support measures by selfless people of our people as a partner, shows humanitarianism in the principles of the reforms being carried out in our country.

As a result of large-scale reforms in the Armed Forces system, we are always proud to show the bravery of our national heroes such as Shiroq, Tomaris, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Najmuddin Kubro, Amir Temur, Babur as an example to our military personnel. The system of the Armed Forces has been greatly improved in terms of organization and structure. [4]

The mobility of structures, combat capability, and physical and moral training of the military have increased. Units and units are equipped with modern weapons and combat equipment. The high fighting ability of the Armed Forces is the most important principle of the cohesion of the people of Uzbekistan and the education of every citizen in the spirit of patriotism through the development of economic, political, strategic and military-technical and scientific power. Therefore, due to the large-scale work in the military field, strict discipline and spiritual-enlightenment thinking will rise.

The task now is that every citizen of New Uzbekistan should be loyal to his job through responsibility and duty, feeling that the basis of the principle of the movement strategy to the development strategy is the development of the country, people's well-being, peace of the country, social cooperation, religious tolerance, inter-ethnic harmony and ideals of the perfect human being.

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